

RADIOACTIVE DECAY

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Annotation.

The term 'radioactive decay' is used in the Uzbek language, although its core terminology originates from international scientific nomenclature. This article explains the fundamental concepts and calculations related to radioactive decay.

Keywords.

Radioactive decay, alpha decay, beta decay, gamma decay, half-life, electron capture, exponential functions, differential equation, radiocarbon method, C-14 isotope, nuclear physics, radiation, ionizing radiation, mass reduction.

Introduction.

To analyze the origin of this term, attention must be given to its components:

Radioactive:

This word derives from the Latin 'radius,' meaning 'ray.' The phenomenon of radioactivity was discovered at the end of the 19th century and the term became widely used in scientific literature of that time.

Decay:

This is an Uzbek word meaning 'fragmentation' or 'disintegration.' It is used to describe the process of atomic nuclei of radioactive substances breaking apart.

Radioactive decay is the process by which unstable atomic nuclei break down into smaller nuclei or other particles, emitting ionizing radiation. This process can occur naturally or be induced artificially.

Main Part. Types of Radioactive Decay

1. Alpha Decay

An alpha particle (${}^2_4\text{He}$, composed of 2 protons and 2 neutrons) is emitted from the nucleus.

As a result, the atomic number decreases by 2 units, and the mass number decreases by 4 units.

Example:

2. Beta Decay

A neutron transforms into a proton, emitting a beta particle (electron). The atomic number increases by 1 unit, but the mass number remains unchanged.

Example:

3. Gamma Decay

The nucleus releases excess energy in the form of gamma radiation. The mass number and atomic number remain unchanged. Gamma decay often occurs after alpha or beta decay.

4. Positron Emission

A proton transforms into a neutron, emitting a positron (e^+). The atomic number decreases by 1 unit, while the mass number remains unchanged.

4. Electron Capture

The nucleus captures an electron from the surrounding electron cloud, converting a proton into a neutron.

The atomic number decreases by 1 unit, and the mass number remains unchanged.

Applications

In Medicine: Radiotherapy, X-ray diagnostics.

In Energy: Power generation at nuclear power plants.

In Archaeology: Dating using the radiocarbon (^{14}C) method.

In Military: Nuclear weapons.

Radioactive Decay Equation

Let $m(t)$ represent the mass of a radioactive substance at time t . It is known from physics that the rate of radioactive decay is proportional to the remaining mass of the substance, that is:

$$m' = -km \quad (1)$$

where $k = \text{const} > 0$ is the proportionality coefficient.

Thus, $m = m(t)$ satisfies the separable differential equation (1). Solving it yields the general solution:

$$m = ce^{(-kt)}$$

If the initial mass at time $t = 0$ is $m_0 > 0$, then $c = m_0$, and the mass changes according to:

$$m = m_0 e^{-kt} \quad (2)$$

Over time, the mass decreases exponentially towards zero.

Half-Life

The half-life T is the time required for half of the initial radioactive substance to decay.

Setting $m(T) = m_0/2$ gives:

$$m_0/2 = m_0 e^{-kT}$$

which leads to:

$$T = (\ln 2)/k \quad \text{or} \quad k = (\ln 2)/T.$$

This formula allows determining k if T is known (which is relatively easy to measure).

Application to Radiocarbon Dating

It is known that living organisms absorb C-14 isotopes from the atmosphere along with stable C-12 carbon. During the life of an organism, the ratio of C-14 to C-12 remains constant at some value m_0 . Upon death, the intake of C-14 stops, and its amount begins to decrease.

The half-life of C-14 is approximately 5570 years. Therefore:

$$k = \ln 2 / 5570 \approx 1.24 \times 10^{-4} \text{ year}^{-1}.$$

Thus, the mass of C-14 at time t after death is:

$$m(t) = m_0 e^{-t/8000}.$$

If $m(t)$ is determined (for instance, by measuring the emitted particles), then the time elapsed since the death of the organism can be calculated by:
 $t = 8000 \times \ln(m_0/m(t)).$

This formula allows determining the age of ancient organic materials.

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